

The role of IPLCs in encouraging businesses to protect nature

IPBES business and biodiversity assessment, Chapter 6 - Contributing Author, Joan Carling, Indigenous Peoples Rights International (IPRI), E: joan@iprights.org

Indigenous Peoples (IPs) play a critical role in conserving biodiversity and protecting the environment. Their traditional knowledge, sustainable practices, and lifestyles of living in harmony with nature provide critical values, principles and practices that can guide responsible business conduct to protect nature. Based on this, Indigenous Peoples can participate meaningfully in designing equitable business models that integrate sustainability and cultural sensitiveness at the core of their operations. Thus, a business regulatory framework that respects the rights of Indigenous Peoples and prioritizes sustainability and social equity can ensure businesses contribute positively to environmental conservation and social inclusion.

Numerous lessons have been learned from the interaction between businesses, biodiversity, and Indigenous Peoples that are critical in addressing barriers in creating an enabling environment to enhance the contributions and roles of Indigenous Peoples. Businesses have realized that incorporating traditional knowledge can lead to more effective and sustainable environmental management practices. Likewise, the respect for the rights of Indigenous Peoples including the requirement for Free, Prior, and Informed Consent is crucial. Businesses that have respected this principle have experienced smoother project implementation and stronger community relations. Further, legal frameworks that recognize and enforce the rights of Indigenous Peoples over their lands and resources can deter businesses from engaging in environmentally harmful activities. Additionally, business regulatory frameworks for participatory conduct of social, cultural and environmental impact assessments and human rights due diligence lead to more appropriate project designs, managing impacts, and sustainable outcomes. Effective mechanisms for shared planning, managements and monitoring with IPs lead to more improved collaboration on resource management and social benefits. These inclusive measures ensure that the voices of those most affected by environmental decisions are accounted for and they become actors and not victims. IP's emphasis on intergenerational equity and sustainable use of resources provides businesses the value of long-term planning over short-term gains. This perspective helps in maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem services essential for future generations. Understanding and respecting the cultural values of IPLCs can prevent conflicts and foster mutual respect.

Indigenous Peoples monitoring systems is one of the most effective ways that Indigenous Peoples can also contribute in ensuring businesses protect the environment. These systems leverage the indigenous knowledge of local ecosystems, providing accurate and real-time data on environmental changes. IPs can help monitor the impacts of corporate activities on biodiversity and can then make them accountable for their environmental footprint and adopt more sustainable practices. This data can also highlight the location and areas most at risk of biodiversity loss and degradation from business activities. It will thereby ensure more responsible sourcing of materials in the supply chain of businesses. Such initiatives not only protect the environment but also promote transparency and accountability within the business sector. Examples of these include commercial logging, agri-business, energy and mining activities. Finally, it is important for Indigenous Peoples affected by business operations to have access to grievance mechanisms to prevent address potential environmental and social harms and to ensure that Indigenous Peoples are able to play their invaluable roles as stewards of biodiversity.